

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 5th – 11th October 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

October 8, 2020 (JAMA Oto.)

Timing, Complications, and Safety of Tracheotomy in Critically Ill Patients With COVID-19

Francesc Xavier Avilés-Jurado, Daniel Prieto-Alhambra, Nesly González-Sánchez et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamaoto.2020.3641>

This cohort study assesses the complications, safety and timing of tracheotomy performed for critically ill patients with COVID-19.

October 7, 2020 (JAMA Netw. Open)

Analysis of Genomic Characteristics and Transmission Routes of Patients With Confirmed SARS-CoV-2 in Southern California During the Early Stage of the US COVID-19 Pandemic

Wenjuan Zhang, John Paul Govindavari, Brian D. Davis et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.24191>

This case series examines the genomic characteristics of SARS-CoV-2 infections and transmission routes during the early stages of the COVID-19 outbreak in Los Angeles, California.

October 7, 2020 (Clin. Cardiology)

The potential association between common comorbidities and severity and mortality of coronavirus disease 2019: A pooled analysis

Liman Luo, Menglu Fu, Yuanyuan Li

<https://doi.org/10.1002/clc.23465>

The association between underlying comorbidities and cardiac injury and the prognosis in COVID-19 patients were assessed in this study. A total of 124 studies were included in this pooled analysis. The authors found that co-morbidities and acute cardiac injury are closely associated with poor prognosis in COVID-19 patients.

October 7, 2020 (World Psych. Assoc.)

Increased risk of COVID-19 infection and mortality in people with mental disorders: analysis from electronic health records in the United States

QuanQiu Wang, Rong Xu, Nora D. Volkow

<https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20806>

This study assessed the impact of a recent (within past year) diagnosis of a mental disorder – including attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), bipolar disorder, depression and schizophrenia – on the risk for COVID-19 infection and related mortality and hospitalization rates. The authors find that individuals with a recent diagnosis of a mental disorder are at an increased risk for COVID-19 infection, which is further exacerbated among African Americans and women. They also found that there was a higher frequency of some adverse outcomes of the infection among this population. This evidence highlights the need to identify and address modifiable vulnerability factors for COVID-19 infection and to prevent delays in health care provision in this population.

October 6, 2020 (JAMA)

Effect of Hydrocortisone on 21-Day Mortality or Respiratory Support Among Critically Ill Patients With COVID-19: A Randomized Clinical Trial
Pierre-François Dequin, Nicholas Heming, Ferhat Meziani, et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.16761>

This randomized clinical trial compares the effect of low-dose hydrocortisone vs placebo on treatment failure (death or persistent respiratory support dependency) at 21 days in critically ill patients with COVID-19 and acute respiratory failure in France. The authors found that low-dose hydrocortisone did not significantly reduce treatment failure in patients with COVID-19–related acute respiratory failure. However, the study was stopped early and was therefore likely underpowered.

October 6, 2020 (JAMA)

Effect of Dexamethasone on Days Alive and Ventilator-Free in Patients With Moderate or Severe Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome and COVID-19: The CoDEX Randomized Clinical Trial
Bruno M. Tomazini, Israel S. Maia, Alexandre B. Cavalcanti et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.17021>

This open-label clinical trial compares the effects of dexamethasone vs usual care on the number of days alive and free of mechanical ventilation at day 28 among COVID-19 patients in Brazil with moderate to severe ARDS. The authors found that intravenous dexamethasone plus standard care, compared with standard of care alone, resulted in a statistically significant increase in the number of days alive and free of mechanical ventilation over 28 days.

October 6, 2020 (JAMA)

Association Between Administration of Systemic Corticosteroids and Mortality Among Critically Ill Patients With COVID-19: A Meta-analysis
The WHO Rapid Evidence Appraisal for COVID-19 Therapies (REACT) Working Group

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.17023>

This meta-analysis pools data from 7 randomized trials to estimate the association between administration of corticosteroids vs usual care or placebo and all-cause mortality at 28 days in patients with COVID-19.

October 5, 2020 (JAMA Pediatr.)

Simulated Assessment of Pharmacokinetically Guided Dosing for Investigational Treatments of Pediatric Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019

Anil R. Maharaj, Huali Wu, Christoph P. Hornik et al.

<https://doi.10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.2422>

This pharmacokinetic simulation study estimates appropriate pediatric-specific dosing regimens for hydroxychloroquine and remdesivir in the treatment of paediatric patients with COVID-19.

September 22, 2020 (PNAS)

Transmission dynamics reveal the impracticality of COVID-19 herd immunity strategies

S. Brett and Pejman Rohani

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2008087117>

Establishing herd immunity in a population by allowing the epidemic to spread, while mitigating the negative health impacts of COVID-19, presents a tantalizing resolution to the COVID-19 crisis. In this study simulating SARS-CoV-2 spread in the United Kingdom, the authors find that achieving herd immunity without overwhelming hospital capacity leaves little room for error. Intervention levels must be carefully manipulated adaptively for an extended period, despite acute sensitivity to poorly quantified epidemiological factors. Such fine-tuning of social distancing renders this strategy impractical.

September 17, 2020 (Nature Communications)

A systematic review of antibody mediated immunity to coronaviruses: kinetics, correlates of protection, and association with severity

Angkana T. Huang, Bernardo Garcia-Carreras, Matt D. T. Hitchings

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18450-4>

The authors review the scientific literature on antibody immunity to coronaviruses, including SARS-CoV-2 as well as the related SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV and endemic human coronaviruses (HCoVs) with a view that evidence from other coronaviruses can provide clues and guide future research.

August 18, 2020 ([Advances in Biomarker Sciences and Technology](#))
Biomarkers of COVID-19 and technologies to combat SARS-CoV-2
Luoping Zhang, Helen Guo
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.abst.2020.08.001>

Biomarkers play a pivotal role in the early detection of disease aetiology, diagnosis, treatment and prognosis. To assist myriad ongoing investigations and innovations, the authors developed this current article to overview known and emerging biomarkers for SARS-CoV-2 detection, COVID-19 diagnostics, treatment and prognosis, and ongoing work to identify and develop more biomarkers for new drugs and vaccines.

B. Science and Engineering

September 24, 2020 ([Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences](#))
Physics of virus transmission by speaking droplets
Roland R. Netz, William A. Eaton
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2011889117>

Netz and Eaton present simple algebraic equations that capture the essential physics of the problem. Calculations with these equations provide a straightforward way of determining whether emitted droplets remain airborne or rapidly fall to the ground. At a relative humidity of 50%, for example, droplets with initial radii larger than about 50 μm rapidly fall to the ground, while smaller, potentially virus-containing droplets shrink in size from water evaporation and remain airborne for many minutes. Their findings support the proposal that mouth coverings can help contain the COVID-19 pandemic.

September 22, 2020 ([Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences](#))
Transmission dynamics reveal the impracticality of COVID-19 herd immunity strategies
Tobias S. Brett and Pejman Rohani
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2008087117>

There are two categories: “mitigation” to achieve herd immunity and “suppression” to drastically reduce SARS-CoV-2 transmission rates and stop endogenous transmission. The authors use an age-structured transmission model, parameterized to simulate SARS-CoV-2 transmission in the United Kingdom, they then assessed the long-term prospects of

success using both of these approaches. They simulated a range of different nonpharmaceutical intervention scenarios incorporating social distancing applied to different age groups. The modelling confirmed that suppression of SARS-CoV-2 transmission is possible with plausible levels of social distancing over months, consistent with observation.

September 23, 2020 (BMC Infect. Dis.)

Modelling and predicting the spatio-temporal spread of COVID-19 in Italy.

Giuliani, D., Dickson, M.M., Espa, G. *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-020-05415-7>

The trend of COVID-19 epidemics in Italy has been analyzed along with time and space. The use of spatio-temporal models at a provincial level greatly improves the predictions of the number of infected people and can help the public decision-makers to better plan health policy interventions.

September 18, 2020 (Science)

Assessing the impact of coordinated COVID-19 exit strategies across Europe

N. W. Ruktanonchai, J. R. Floyd, S. Lai *et al.*

<http://doi.org/10.1126/science.abc5096>

The authors use mobility and case data to quantify how coordinated exit strategies could delay continental resurgence and limit community transmission of COVID-19. They find that a resurgent epidemic could occur as early as 5 weeks when stringent existing interventions end their interventions prematurely. They argue that appropriate coordination can greatly reduce community transmission throughout Europe.

September 18, 2020 (Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal)

An immersive journey to the molecular structure of SARS-CoV-2: Virtual reality in COVID-19

Martin Calvelo, Angel Pineiro, Rebeca Garcia-Fandino.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2020.09.018>

The proper understanding of the three-dimensional structures that compose the virus, as well as of those involved in the infection process and treatments, is expected to contribute to the advance of fundamental and applied research against this pandemic, including basic molecular biology studies and drug design. Virtual reality (VR) is used to visualize the biomolecular structures or SARS-CoV-2 in the understanding of the disease-associated mechanisms. They review the software implementations currently available for VR visualization of SARS-CoV-2 molecular structures, covering a range of virtual environments: CAVEs, desktop software, and cell phone applications.

August 27, 2020 (Scientific Data)

HIT-COVID, a global database tracking public health intervention to COVID-19

Qulu Zheng, Forrest K. Jones, Sarah V. Leavitt et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-00610-2>

Quantifying the effectiveness of these interventions in reducing disease transmission is key to rational policy-making in response to the current and future pandemics. To estimate their effectiveness, detailed descriptions of their timelines, scale and scope are needed. The Health Intervention Tracking for COVID-19 is a global database that catalogues the implementation and relaxation of COVID-19 related social measures. They continue to adapt to this database to serve as a resource for others.

September 28, 2020 (Applied Soft Computing)

Sentiment Analysis of COVID-19 tweets by Deep Learning Classifiers -A study to show how popularity is affecting accuracy in social media

Koyel Chakraborty, Surbhi Bhatia, Siddhartha Bhattacharyya.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106754>

This paper shows that tweets containing all handles related to COVID-19 and WHO have been unsuccessful in advising people. The analysis reveals that the maximum number of tweets portrays neutral or negative sentiments. A dataset containing 226,668 tweets analysed between December 2019 and May 2020 show that there were a maximum number of positive and neutral tweets tweeted by netizens. However, the research demonstrates that though people have tweeted mostly positive messages, yet some were busy re-tweeting the negative messages and that no useful words could be found in WordCloud or from word frequency in tweets. They validated through a proposed model using deep learning classifiers with accuracy up to 81%.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

September 24, 2020 (World Development)

Industrial policy for sustainable human development in the post-COVID19 era

Andrea Ferrannini, Elisa Barbieri, Mario Biggeri et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105215>

In this paper, the authors argue that a turning point on the connection between industrial policy, sustainability and development has been reached. They highlight the need to reconsider its theoretical foundations, governance and implementation processes for a new role in the post-COVID 19 societies. They raise questions on industrial policy and its effects on human development, social cohesion and sustainability. They

hope to contribute to the debate on post-Covid19 economies and societies by providing a new integrated analytical framework on industrial policy.

September 5, 2020 (Health Policy and Technology)

An analysis of the policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in France, Belgium, and Canada

Zachary Desson, Emmi Weller, Peter McMeekin et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.09.002>

This paper presents an overview and analysis of the epidemiological situation and the policy responses in France, Belgium and Canada during the early stages of the pandemic (Feb till Aug 2020). A review of data from France, Belgium and Canada faced differing epidemiological situations and the policy actions taken are linked to the existing governance and healthcare structures. The varying degrees of federalism and regional autonomy highlight the different constraints faced by national policy-makers within different governance models.

August 28, 2020 (Health Policy and Technology)

The COVID-19 pandemic in Greece, Iceland, New Zealand, and Singapore: Health policies and lessons learned.

Ayman Fouda, Nader Mahmoudi, Naomi Moy et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlpt.2020.08.015>

This paper reviews the COVID-19 situation, health policies and economic impact in Greece, Iceland, New Zealand and Singapore. They use document analysis based on national reports, media announcements, official coronavirus websites and governmental decrees. These countries have different demographic, epidemiological, socioeconomic profiles but managed to control the pandemic. Early proactive and strict interventions along with applying previous experience on communicable diseases contributed to the success.